
**Corporate Governance and Performance measurement
on Private and state-owned banks of Bangladesh**

Project Report

EAST WEST UNIVERSITY

Project Report On

**Corporate Governance and Performance measurement
on Private and state-owned banks of Bangladesh**

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Chapter 1: Introduction

Corporate Governance has become a topical because of its immense contribution to growth and development of nations. The absence good corporate governance is a major cause of failure of many while performing companies. Corporate governance is the system of rules, practices and processes by which a company is directed and controlled. Corporate governance essentially involves balancing the interests of a company's many stakeholders, such as shareholders, management, customers, suppliers, financiers, government and the community. Since corporate governance also provides the framework for attaining a company's objectives, it encompasses practically every sphere of management, from action plans and internal controls to performance measurement and corporate disclosure. According to Shleifer and Vishny corporate governance deals with the ways in which suppliers of finance to corporations assure themselves of getting a return on their investment. The purpose of corporate governance is to facilitate effective, entrepreneurial and prudent management that can deliver the long-term success of the company. Corporate governance is therefore about what the board of a company does and how it sets the values of the company, and it is to be distinguished from the day-to-day operational management of the company. The importance of corporate governance are I) Corporate Governance Promotes community confidence II) Encourages elected members and council officers to be confident III) Leads to better decisions IV) Helps local government meet its legislative responsibilities V) Supports ethical decision making. Cash is an important asset for any corporation. Cash is one of the assets which shows the assets portion in the balance sheet of every firm. Cash is playing a vital role in the finances of a firm. The corporate governess and performance measurement are most related in every firm because it does not relate to private firms that are not played in the long run. Performance measurement is an important factor for financial management, this is not only related to operations and improvement of firms but also relates to the corporate governances Firm's performance is measured to be dependent variable is performance measurement (ROA, ROE) whereas independent variable is corporate governance Bank's Size, Capital Adequacy, liquidity ratio, operation management , non-performing loans ratio , Board size, Board meeting ,Duality , Independent Director , GDP per capita growth .

1.1 Background of the study:

This paper examines the variables that impact banks' success in Bangladesh. I pick eleven private banks and public banks as a sample to find those variables, and I also try to find out their data on variables over the last two years (2019 & 2020). I implemented four types of variables for the calculation of variables. These are: profitability, bank-specific determinants, economic determinants, and bank governance. I have used two types of factors in the case of profitability, which are Return on Assets and Return on Equity. On the other hand, under bank-specific determinants, I took five variables-the size of the bank, the capital adequacy ratio, the cost-to - income ratio, the liquidity ratio and the non-performing loans ratio. I took four factors, which are Board Size, Duality, Board Meetings and Independent Directors, as GDP as a variable. I measure the average outcome of those variables after defining them, and aim to find statistical values, such as mean, median, minimum and maximum standard deviation. I try to figure out the correlation between ROA and independent variables after that and also the correlation between ROE and independent variables. We may define the relationship between dependent variables and independent variables using this term. After the correlation is identified, I want to figure out the implications of the panel regression. As a consequence, the factors or variables influencing Bangladesh's banking efficiency can be easily established. I also try to offer theoretical reasons in this analysis to understand which variables influence Bangladesh's banking efficiency.

1.2 Significance of the Study:

The objectives of the study are as follows:

- To analyze the performance of Bangladeshi banks.
- To identify the factors that influence the performance of the Bangladeshi banking sector.
- To find out how those factors or variables can influence the Bangladeshi banking industry

1.3 Research contribution:

This study is focused on 11 of Bangladesh's private banks and public banks. I try to figure out their logical data, such as Asset Return, Equity Return, Capital Adequacy Ratio, Benefit Cost Ratio. Non-Performing Percentage of Loans, board size, bank size and many more. I will do Correlation matrix and panel regression analysis after seeking reasonable data to figure out which variables influence Bangladesh's banking industry results. Both qualitative and quantitative research methods will be employed to achieve the goals of this article and to determine the relationship between corporate governance and firm performance. The major goal of this paper is to determine the relationship between corporate governance and business performance, as well as the extent to which corporate governance influences firm performance. In order to obtain this information, I try to conduct an exploratory study.

1.4 Limitation of the study:

While preparing this report, some barriers were faced including:

- Limitation of time.
- Collecting information from the website was very difficult for me because it is not enriched with information, although I tried my hardest to collect full data.
- Employees are not allowed to provide sensitive and depth information or confidential data.
- The data contained in this report are also collected from secondary sources because of lacking in primary data collection, so the authenticity of the report may be questionable to some people.

1.5 Research Objective

- To find out the relationship (positive or negative) among corporate governance and performance measurement.
- To find out whether board size has any impact on firm performance.
- To find out whether audit committee size has any impact on performance measurement.
- To identify the importance of board and management skill level on firm performance.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

Bourke (1989) Between 1972 and 1981, researchers looked at the success of banks in 12 nations across Europe, North America, and Australia. Focus, liquidity, inflation, and scale, he found, all had a favorable impact on bank efficiency and profitability. The technique of Bourke (1989) is replicated in Molyneux and Thornton's (1992) investigation. Between 1986 and 1989, the determinants of banking success were studied in 18 European nations. The findings backed up Bourke's observations. Return on average assets (ROAA) is a method of determining a bank's efficiency.

Pasiouras and Kosmidou (2007) In the years 1995-2001, the profitability of 584 commercial domestic and foreign banks operating in the 15 European Union nations was examined. The results reveal that the profitability of local and multinational banks in the European Union is impacted by basic bank attributes (size, capital adequacy, managerial efficiency 1857-7431), financial market infrastructure (concentration), and macroeconomic indicators (growth rate of profit).

In addition, Athanasoglou et al. (2008) Between 1985 and 2001, a study was released to examine the effects of bank-specific, industry-specific, and macroeconomics variables of Greek bank profitability. Except for the size of the business, the calculations revealed that all bank-specific characteristics had a significant impact on transaction profitability. The research also revealed that bank profitability is unaffected by concentration and governance..

De Andres and Vallelado (2008) From 1995 to 2005, a sample of 69 major commercial bank boards from Canada, France, the United Kingdom, Italy, Spain, and the United States were used. They discovered that bank success was strongly linked to board meetings, with an inverted U-shaped relationship between board size and the share of outside directors.

(Murtaza, 2020) argued that by the second half of 2020, the majority of banks will be in a precarious position in terms of operating earnings. Almost all of the banks have experienced a gradual increase in profits when compared to the previous year. indicated that the banking industry is experiencing liquidity and loan recovery issues.

(Kumar, D., Z;, Hossain, ., & Islam, S, 2020) NPLs are the issues and challenges facing Bangladesh's banking system, according to the report. Administrative softness, poor governance, and a lack of political will have been identified as important contributors in bank businesses' dissatisfaction.

Trujillo-Ponce (2013) From 1999 to 2009, researchers looked into the elements that influenced the performance of Spanish banks. Following that, the analysis reveals inefficiencies in the efficiency of commercial and savings banks. Second, Asset quality, capitalization, concentrations, inflation, economic expansion, and real interest rates all showed a strong positive association, according to the data, as well as between ROA and ROE. Finally, when it came to the impact of bank size on profitability, the findings found that size had no effect on the two profitability criteria. Numerous authors have reported on studies on the impact of corporate governance on bank results.

Liang et al. (2013) The qualities of the board's effect on bank efficiency and bank asset valuation in China were investigated. They found that the composition of the board had a significant The proportion of independent directors and the number of board meetings had a significant positive influence on both bank performance and asset quality, whereas the proportion of independent directors and the number of board meetings had a large negative impact., using panel data from the 50 largest Chinese banks from 2003 to 2010.

Staikouras et al. (2007) Over the year 2002-2004, researchers looked examined the relationship between two of the most important corporate governance metrics – the size of the board of directors and the number of non-executive directors – and the firm production of 58 large European banks. The findings show that bank profitability is inversely correlated with board size, but the influence of board structure, while positive in all models, is minor in most circumstances.

Covid-19 has effects on shape and mind and is breaking the concept of the world economy and global village. Even the globe's life science is deteriorating to curb the disease.

(Mahmud, Z. U. (2020), 2021) the banking sector is intertwined with the economy, and its strength depends not only on its strategy, but also on the expansion of the country's other sectors.

Samad (2015) examines the impact of the bank's basic and macroeconomic variables on the banking sector's viability in Bangladesh. The study used data from 42 commercial banks in Bangladesh as part of a panel data collection. To evaluate the effect of bank earnings, the study employed bank-specific variables such as bank financial risk, bank operating performance, and bank scale, as well as macro-economic variables such as economic growth. Considerations such as the loan-to-deposit ratio, total asset loan-loss allocation, total asset equity resources, and total asset operating costs, according to the report, are key factors. Earnings are unaffected by the size of the bank or macroeconomic conditions.

Akhtar, Ali, Sadaqat (2011) used panel data for Pakistani banks from 2006 to 2009 and found a gearing ratio, non-performing loans, and asset management that had a substantial effect on the profitability of traditional Pakistani banks.

Macit (2011), paper on Turkish commercial banks, a Turkish scholar found that the non-performing loan percentage is negatively related to return on assets and return on equity, which has an impact on the banking sector's success.

Shamim, (2019) Bangladeshi banks are facing vast uncertainties and skepticism particularly about refunds of credits by their customers when their commercial activities are in disarray.

Babu, (2020) Nonperforming loans are those that leave banks but do not return to their records, resulting in a loss of financial health. When a bank's bad loan rate is high, it weakens the bank's ability to offer loans and puts stockholders at risk.

Berle and Means (1932) and even earlier Smith (1776). Zingales (1998) Allocation of ownership, capital structure, managerial incentive schemes, takeovers, board of directors, pressure from institutional investors, skepticism competition, labor market competition, organizational structure, and other institutions can all be thought of as institutions that affect the process through which quasi-rents are distributed," according to the definition of corporate governance.

Shleifer and Vishny (1997) How suppliers of money to firms ensure that they will earn a return on their investment" is how corporate governance is defined. Corporate governance is the method by which business corporations are directed and governed," according to the OECD in 1999. The corporate governance structure spells out the rules and methods for making corporate decisions, as well as the distribution of rights and obligations among different players in the organization, such as the board of directors, managers, shareholders, and other stakeholders. It also offers the structure through which the company's goals are realized, as well as the means of achieving those goals and measuring performance.

Oman (2001) Company governance is defined as rules, regulations, and business practices that govern the relationship between corporate managers and stakeholders in both private and public institutions. Corporate governance is defined by the Singapore Ministry of Finance (corporate governance 2001) as "the processes and structure by which the company's business and affairs are directed and managed, to enhance long-term shareholder value through corporate mechanism. As a result, good corporate governance encapsulates both enterprise performance and accountability, as well as adherence..

La Porta, Silanes, and Shleifer (2000, 2002) Consider corporate governance to be a set of procedures that safeguard outside investors (shareholders) from insiders (managers). Corporate governance is defined by the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development as the framework by which business corporations are directed and governed. The corporate governance structure defines out the rules and methods for making corporate decisions, as well as the distribution of rights and obligations among different players in the organization, such as the Board of Directors, management, shareholders, and other stakeholders. It also offers the frameworks through which the company's goals are determined, as well as the means of achieving those goals and monitoring performance.

McColgan (2001) presented a comprehensive perspective on agency theory and corporate governance His research was primarily focused on the region where the interests of managers differ from the interests of shareholders. He kept the agency relationship in mind, as well as the agency expense that comes with it. He built on Jensen and Meckling's definition of an agency relationship as a type of contract in which the principal retains the agent to perform the firm's services on his behalf. As the principal delegate some decision-making authority to the, the agency dilemma occurs owing to competing interests and a conflict between ownership and control.

Okeahalam and Akinboade (2003) stated that corporate governance is intimately concerned with organizational systems, procedures, processes, and norms of governing institutions, therefore there is a need to find those relationships that control, generate, or decide the nature of relationships through those interactions. Companies should balance the interests of shareholders and stakeholders at all levels of the company, according to corporate governance.

Farinha (2003) noted that a fundamental issue in a business is the interaction between principal and agent relationships, as well as the manager's differing perspective from that of the shareholders. The manager's perspective remains limited cash-flows, therefore the manager's concentration is on a short-term investment strategy, whereas shareholders are stuck with a speedy return of cash flows. The principal and the agent's risk preferences are also a key source of contention. Their survival is dependent on it. External disciplining devices are absent in the field of corporate governance. These devices can be implemented by businesses with good corporate governance.

Filatotchev, Lien, and Piesse (2004) studied Corporate Governance and Performance in Taiwanese Publicly Listed, Family-Owned Businesses. They looked at the impact of ownership structure and board characteristics on performance in large, publicly traded companies run by family businesses. The authors

stated that East Asian enterprises operate in a different culture and legal and institutional context than firms in the West and Europe, and that these cultural variations may have a significant impact on governance-performance linkages, as shown by agency and strategy research. The authors found no direct link between family ownership and management entrenchment and extraction of private gains from this control, which could be a contributing factor to poor financial performance.

Lien and Piesse (2004) indicated that the process of globalization may bring foreign investors to Taiwan's marketplaces, resulting in good corporate governance being imported by Taiwanese enterprises. Family control over the executive board is also a crucial factor of performance, according to the findings of their study. The corporate governance of bank mergers and acquisitions was addressed by Becher and Campbell (2004). He believed that during mergers and acquisitions, CEOs bargain for their own interests while the company's outside directors confront financial difficulties. Independent companies' corporate governance had a significant impact.

Becher and Campbell (2004) Using a sample of 146 significant US bank mergers during the 1990s, he conducted an empirical study to determine the effects of personal perks and merger premiums. They looked at the two thousand directors and executives involved in these mergers and discovered that the target's merger premium is inversely proportional to the number of target directors retained. This includes things like the size of the company, incentives, payment methods, and bidder returns. The three studies indicated that the target director's interests are more concerned with the company's size than with its performance, and that they use their bargaining leverage with the acquirer to offset the interests of shareholders in the merger.

Novikova (2004) studied the impact of a firm's internal corporate governance system on its innovative activities, and how much a firm's internal corporate governance system varies with the nature and efficiency of its innovative activities. The board, the shareholders, the management, and other stakeholders for the enterprises are listed by Novikova (2004) as significant participatory actors for the firms. He described institutions as the norms and procedures that are used to make judgments about the firm's corporate affairs. Cueto (2007) The relationship between corporate governance and business value, as well as the implications of ownership structure and stock market liquidity, should be investigated, according to the proposal. to determine the role of ownership mechanisms and corporate governance practices in Latin America's rising market

Kowalewski et al. (2007) studied authors' perspectives in their large literature on the subject were examined, and it was discovered that corporate governance is a key driver for explaining dividend policy, according to empirical implications. They also discovered that larger asset-retaining enterprises and highly successful firms with limited investment prospects pay higher dividends, while high-risk and indebted companies pay lower dividends. Companies with excellent corporate governance procedures and strong shareholder rights pay larger dividends in Poland, which helps to minimize the country's agency issues.

Chapter 3 Research methodology

3.1 Methodology

of the Study When I am making this project, every data is collected from the secondary sources.

3.1.1 Secondary sources

The secondary sources that I used for this project are

- Website
- Annual Report of different banks
- Previous Research Report
- Different article

3.2 Variables

Variables	Category	Variables	Measures	Notation	Expected effect
Dependent variables	Profitability	Return on Assets	Net Profit/Total Assets	ROA	+/-
		Return on Equity	Net Profit/Equity	ROE	
Independent		Bank's Size	Natural(normal) logarithm of total asset of the bank	SIZE	+

variables	Bank-specific determinants	Capital Adequacy ratio	Equity to total assets	CA	+/-
		Liquidity	Liquid assets/(deposit + borrowings)	LIQ	+/-
		Operating Management	Cost to income ratio	COST	+/-
		Non-Performing Loans Ratio	Non-Performing Loans/Total Loans	NPL	+/-
		Board Size	The number of members in the board	BS	+/-
		Board Meetings	The number of board meetings	MEET	+

BANK	year	Dependent variables				Independent variables							
		Profitability		Bank's Size	Bank-specific determinants			Bank governance			Macroeconomic determinants		
		ROA	ROE		Capital Adequacy	Liquidity ratio	COST	NPL	Meetings	BS	DUA	IND	GDP
Brac bank	2020	1.18	10.58	5.56	15.13	12.1	64	2.93	9	16	1	33	5.7
	2019	1.64	15.6	5.5	16.16	11.67	60	3.99	8	17	0	38	2.6
	Average	1.41	13.09	5.53	15.645	11.885	62	3.46	8.5	16.5	0.5	35.5	4.15
DBBL	2020	1.3	18.4	5.54	17.2	3.36	68.1	2.2	7	15	1	29	10.5
	2019	1.2	17.2	5.49	15.5	3.11	69.3	4.4	7	14	0	29	19.86
	Average	1.3	18.4	5.54	17.2	3.36	68.1	2.2	7	15	1	29	10.5
Megna Bank	2020	0.22	8.9	10.64	11.31	7.44	43.12	2.6	20	20	0	0	-4.52
	2019	0.19	7.6	8.89	9.41	6.14	55.78	2.1	20	18	1	0	6.49
	Average	0.205	8.25	9.765	10.36	6.79	49.45	2.35	20	19	0.5	0	0.985
Prime Bank	2020	0.54	6.31	5.47	17.28	6.21	2.12	3.46	21	14	1	19	6.15
	2019	0.54	5.93	5.45	17.42	5.54	1.98	4.66	18	22	0	17	6.25
	Average	0.54	6.12	5.46	17.35	5.875	2.05	4.06	19.5	18	0.5	18	6.2
mutual Trust	2020	0.37	5.83	5.35	12.92	7.9	50.31	4.6	12	16	1	8	2.35
	2019	0.56	9.03	5.3	12.91	6.4	53.82	5.39	13	15	0	15	4.17
	Average	0.465	7.43	5.325	12.915	7.15	52.065	4.995	12.5	15.5	0.5	11.5	3.26
One Bank	2020	0.44	0.09	11.42	13.02	4.33	37.41	11.28	9	24	1	22	1.83
	2019	0.59	0.88	5.34	12.8	3.43	29.78	1.25	9	25	0	22	2.64
	Average	0.515	0.485	8.38	12.91	3.88	33.595	6.265	9	24.5	0.5	22	2.235
City Bank	2020	0.21	4.21	12.12	10.02	7.3	74.13	18.37	14	58	0	0	18.99
	2019	0.2	3.92	11.87	10.09	9.64	62.11	20.32	14	46	0	0	15.97
	Average	0.205	4.065	11.995	10.055	8.47	68.12	19.345	14	52	0	0	17.48
Sonali Bank	2020	0.03	0.46	11.94	10.09	5.92	80.69	19.5	8	48	0	0	13.5
	2019	0.33	5.23	5.91	10.06	4.85	78.33	3.73	10	48	0	0	91.03
	Average	0.18	2.845	8.925	10.075	5.385	79.51	11.615	9	48	0	0	52.265
Janata Bank	2020	1	16.59	11.83	10.24	27.86	80.51	17.45	10	23	0	0	2.3
	2019	0.64	14.54	10.87	12.61	24.55	75.64	18.56	10	26	0	0	30.82
	Average	0.82	15.565	11.35	11.425	26.205	78.075	18.005	10	24.5	0	0	16.56
Agrani Bank	2020	0.03	0.92	9.17	8.01	0.54	88.35	12.7	11	24	1	27.27	-39
	2019	0.03	0.8	5.58	10.34	0.67	91.21	16.15	11	21	0	25.47	-9.22
	Average	0.03	0.86	7.375	9.175	0.605	89.78	14.425	11	22.5	0.5	26.37	-24.11
Rupali Bank	2020	1.1	14.8	11.51	15.5	14.6	58	4	13	22	1	15.38	-4.72
	2019	0.7	9.9	5.44	15.2	12.8	53.9	5.8	14	25	0	14.29	-3.73
	Average	0.9	12.35	8.475	15.35	13.7	55.95	4.9	13.5	23.5	0.5	14.835	-4.225

3.3 Data types and source

I collected data from each bank annual report.

3.4 Sample size

The population for this report will be listed private and government own bank. The researcher will take at least six private bank as sample from five government own bank . The companies will be chosen randomly.

3.5 Data collection technique

This paper will develop a summary metric for the governing score that will be used to assess the firm's governing strength. I gathered data on corporate governance and business performance from annual reports and available to the public information sources. Although I will try to obtain data from credible sources such as annual reports and journals, I will largely rely on secondary sources for my study. This paper will use a large number of individual firms as a sample for this study, ensuring that it is representative of real-world events. This article will use data from the 2019 and 2020 fiscal years to assess firm performance.

3.6 data analysis technique

I use some following technique to analysis my overall project

- multiple regression analysis
- correlation
- descripted statistic

3.7 Regression Model

3.7.1 Multiple Regression data analysis of ROA

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.889545223
R Square	0.791290704
Adjusted R Square	0.559391487
Standard Error	0.305467399
Observations	11

ANOVA					
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	10	3.183952016	0.318395202	3.412218092	0.039270928
Residual	7	0.839792984	0.093310332		
Total	17	4.023745			

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>	<i>Lower 95.0%</i>	<i>Upper 95.0%</i>
Intercept	-0.702889631	2.129110805	-0.33013295	0.748854289	-5.51927289	4.11349363	-5.519272889	4.113493628
SIZE	0.130878367	0.204480499	0.640053049	0.538089094	-0.33168866	0.59344539	-0.331688659	0.593445393
CA	0.06994701	0.054000945	1.295292315	0.22745617	-0.05221162	0.19210564	-0.052211616	0.192105635
LIQ	0.022822255	0.013862554	1.646323986	0.134103952	-0.00853702	0.05418153	-0.008537021	0.054181531
COST	-0.006106797	0.007222085	-0.84557254	0.41970299	-0.02244429	0.01023069	-0.022444288	0.010230695
NPL	0.006564591	0.014527006	0.451888815	0.662042671	-0.02629778	0.03942696	-0.026297778	0.039426961
BS	-0.044543495	0.026742781	-1.66562689	0.130141274	-0.10503987	0.01595288	-0.105039868	0.015952878
MEET	-0.012233382	0.014594413	-0.83822365	0.423606982	-0.04524824	0.02078147	-0.045248239	0.020781474
DUA	-0.16936367	0.3530617	-0.47969992	0.642883302	-0.96804472	0.62931738	-0.968044723	0.629317382
IND	0.011948773	0.010267014	1.163802243	0.274428196	-0.01127682	0.03517437	-0.011276825	0.035174372
GDP	-0.005896565	0.004767851	-1.23673416	0.247484634	-0.01668219	0.00488906	-0.016682194	0.004889065

Table Multiple regression results

R square = 0.791290704

Dependent variable (ROA) is explained around 79% by the set of independent variables X_1 (SIZE), X_2 (CA), X_3 (LIQ), X_4 (COST), X_5 (NPL), X_6 (BS), X_7 (MEET), X_8 (DUA), X_9 (IND), X_{10} (GDP)

Adjusted R Square = 0.559391487

Dependent variable (ROA) is explained around 79% by the set of independent variables X_1 (SIZE), X_2 (CA), X_3 (LIQ), X_4 (COST), X_5 (NPL), X_6 (BS), X_7 (MEET), X_8 (DUA), X_9 (IND), X_{10} (GDP)

Significance F =0.039270928

Hypothesis:

$$H_0: b_1 = b_2 = b_3 = b_4 = b_5 = b_6 = b_7 = b_8 = b_9 = b_{10} = 0$$

H_1 : Not all the b_i 's are zero

Evaluating individual regression coefficients:

For SIZE

$$H_0: \beta_1=0$$

$$H_1: \beta_1 \neq 0$$

In this case Probability value 0.538089094 is greater than 0.05 so, H_0 is accepted at 0.05 significance level. So the number of SIZE does not have significant impact on ROA

For CA

$$H_0: \beta_2=0$$

$$H_1: \beta_2 \neq 0$$

In this case Probability value 0.22745617 is greater than 0.05 so, H_0 is accepted at 0.05 significance level. The variable of CA does not have significant impact on ROA if CA increases by 1 unit the ROA increases by 0.06994701

For LIQ

$$H_0: \beta_3=0$$

$$H_1: \beta_3 \neq 0$$

In this case Probability value 0.134103952 is greater than 0.05 so, H_0 is accepted at 0.05 significance level. So the variable of LIQ does not have significant impact on ROA if LIQ increases by 1 unit the ROA decreases 0.022822255

For COST

$$H_0: \beta_4=0$$

$$H_1: \beta_4 \neq 0$$

In this case Probability value 0.41970299 is less than 0.05 so, H_0 is rejected at 0.05 significance level. So the variable of COST has significant impact on ROA if COST increases by 1 unit the ROA decreases

-0.006106797

For NPL

$$H_0: \beta_5=0$$

$$H_1: \beta_5 \neq 0$$

In this case Probability value 0.662042671 is greater than 0.05 so, H_0 is accepted at 0.05 significance level .So the variable of NPL does not have significant impact on ROA if NPL increases by 1 unit ROA increases by 0.006564591

For BS

$$H_0: \beta_6=0$$

$$H_1: \beta_6 \neq 0$$

In this case Probability value 0.130141274 is greater than 0.05 so, H_0 is accepted at 0.05 significance level .So the variable of BS does not have significant impact on ROA if BS increases by 1 unit ROA decreases -0.044543495

For MEET

$$H_0: \beta_7=0$$

$$H_1: \beta_7 \neq 0$$

In this case Probability value 0.423606982 is less than 0.05 so, H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted at 0.05 significance level .So the variable of MEET has significant impact on ROA if MEET increases by 1 unit the ROA decreases -0.012233382

For DUA

$$H_0: \beta_8=0$$

$$H_1: \beta_8 \neq 0$$

In this case Probability value 0.642883302 is greater than 0.05 so, H_0 is accepted at 0.05 significance level .So the variable of DUA does not have significant impact on ROA if DUA increases by 1 unit then ROA decreases -0.16936367

For IND

$$H_0: \beta_9=0$$

$$H_1: \beta_9 \neq 0$$

In this case Probability value 0.274428196 is greater than 0.05 so, H_0 is accepted at 0.05 significance level .So the variable of IND does not have significant impact on total sales if IND increases by 1 unit the ROA increases 0.011948773

For GPD

$$H_0: \beta_{10}=0$$

$$H_1: \beta_{10}\neq 0$$

In this case Probability value 0.247484634 is greater than 0.05 so, H_0 is accepted at 0.05 significance level .So the variable of GPR does not have significant impact on ROA if GPR increases by 1 unit then ROA decreases -0.005896565

$$H_0: b_1=b_2=b_3= b_4=b_5=b_6= b_7 =b_8=b_9= b_{10}=0$$

$$H_1: \text{Not all the } b_i\text{'s are zero}$$

3.7.2 Multiple Regression data analysis of ROE

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.706348093
R Square	0.498927629
Adjusted R Square	-0.05781945
Standard Error	5.753573486
Observations	11

ANOVA					
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	10	296.657229	29.665723	0.8961477	0.569868517
Residual	7	297.932471	33.103608		
Total	17	594.5897			

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>	<i>Lower 95.0%</i>	<i>Upper 95.0%</i>
Intercept	-20.4332528	40.1024644	-0.509526	0.6226415	-111.15133	70.2848244	-111.15133	70.28482435
SIZE	1.58006003	3.85145382	0.4102503	0.6912165	-7.1325338	10.2926539	-7.1325338	10.29265387
CA	0.674370283	1.01712461	0.6630164	0.523936	-1.6265254	2.975266	-1.6265254	2.975266002
LIQ	0.218570043	0.26110552	0.8370947	0.4242089	-0.3720917	0.80923176	-0.3720917	0.809231755
COST	0.041562381	0.13603022	0.3055379	0.7669053	-0.2661594	0.34928411	-0.2661594	0.349284113
NPL	-0.09930062	0.27362067	-0.362913	0.7250466	-0.7182736	0.51967234	-0.7182736	0.519672338
BS	-0.09175387	0.5037086	-0.182157	0.8594966	-1.2312219	1.04771414	-1.2312219	1.047714142
MEE T	-0.07293911	0.27489032	-0.265339	0.7967259	-0.6947842	0.54890599	-0.6947842	0.548905992

DUA	3.081169499	6.65002695	0.4633319	0.6541269	-11.962237	18.1245756	-11.962237	18.1245756
IND	0.142215209	0.19338239	0.7354093	0.4808146	-0.2952462	0.57967658	-0.2952462	0.579676577
GPR	-0.04951399	0.08980396	-0.551356	0.5948109	-0.2526647	0.15363669	-0.2526647	0.153636693

Table 21 Multiple regression results

R square = 0.498927629

Dependent variable (ROE) is explained around 49.9% by the set of independent variables X_1 (SIZE), X_2 (CA), X_3 (LIQ), X_4 (COST), X_5 (NPL), X_6 (BS), X_7 (MEET), X_8 (DUA), X_9 (IND), X_{10} (GDP)

Adjusted R Square = -0.05781945

Dependent variable (ROE) is explained around 49.9% by the set of independent variables X_1 (SIZE), X_2 (CA), X_3 (LIQ), X_4 (COST), X_5 (NPL), X_6 (BS), X_7 (MEET), X_8 (DUA), X_9 (IND), X_{10} (GDP)

Significance F =0.569868517

Hypothesis:

$$H_0: b_1 = b_2 = b_3 = b_4 = b_5 = b_6 = b_7 = b_8 = b_9 = b_{10} = 0$$

H_1 : Not all the b_i 's are zero

Evaluating individual regression coefficients:

For SIZE

$$H_0: \beta_1 = 0$$

$$H_1: \beta_1 \neq 0$$

In this case Probability value 0.6912165 is greater than 0.05 so, H_0 is accepted at 0.05 significance level. So the number of SIZE does not have significant impact on ROE

For CA

$$H_0: \beta_2 = 0$$

$$H_1: \beta_2 \neq 0$$

In this case Probability value 0.523936 is greater than 0.05 so, H_0 is accepted at 0.05 significance level. The variable of CA does not have significant impact on ROE

For LIQ

$$H_0: \beta_3=0$$

$$H_1: \beta_3 \neq 0$$

In this case Probability value 0.4242089 is less than 0.05 so, H_0 is rejected at 0.05 significance level .So the variable of LIQ has significant impact on ROE if LIQ increases by 1 unit then ROE increases 0.218570043

For COST

$$H_0: \beta_4=0$$

$$H_1: \beta_4 \neq 0$$

In this case Probability value 0.41970299 is less than 0.05 so, H_0 is rejected at 0.05 significance level .So the variable of COST has significant impact on ROE if COST increases by 1 unit the ROE increases

0.041562381

For NPL

$$H_0: \beta_5=0$$

$$H_1: \beta_5 \neq 0$$

In this case Probability value 0.662042671 is greater than 0.05 so, H_0 is accepted at 0.05 significance level .So the variable of NPL does not have significant impact on ROE

For BS

$$H_0: \beta_6=0$$

$$H_1: \beta_6 \neq 0$$

In this case Probability value 0.8594966 is greater than 0.05 so, H_0 is accepted at 0.05 significance level .So the variable of BS does not have significant impact on ROE

For MEET

$$H_0: \beta_7=0$$

$$H_1: \beta_7 \neq 0$$

In this case Probability value 0.7967259 is Greater than 0.05 so, H_0 is accepted at 0.05 significance level .So the variable of MEET does not have significant impact on ROE

For DUA

$$H_0: \beta_8=0$$

$$H_1: \beta_8 \neq 0$$

In this case Probability value 0.6541269 is greater than 0.05 so, H_0 is accepted at 0.05 significance level .So the variable of DUA does not have significant impact on ROE

For IND

$$H_0: \beta_9=0$$

$$H_1: \beta_9 \neq 0$$

In this case Probability value 0.4808146 is greater than 0.05 so, H_0 is accepted at 0.05 significance level

So the variable of IND does not have significant impact on ROE

For GPP

$$H_0: \beta_{10}=0$$

$$H_1: \beta_{10} \neq 0$$

In this case Probability value 0.5948109 is greater than 0.05 so, H_0 is accepted at 0.05 significance level .So the variable of GPR does not have significant impact on ROE

Chapter 4 Result and Discussion

4.1 Descriptive analysis

Variable	Mean	Median	Std. Dev	Min	Max
ROA	0.82	0.8125	0.422592251	0.18	1.715

ROE	10.26025	10.55	5.609891048	0.485	20.04
SIZE	7.4365	6.475	2.297629843	5.32	11.995
CA	12.293	12.26	1.371731906	10.075	15.05
LIQ	9.59525	8.06	6.2264025	0.605	26.205
COST	52.0075	50.3175	19.40453986	2.05	89.78
NPL	6.71325	4.645	6.357057884	0.215	27.87
BS	12.6	12.25	3.861415066	7	20
MEET	24.975	23.75	10.07011603	14.5	52
DUA	0.425	0.5	0.293571474	0	1
IND	17.29675	18	10.71335569	0	35.5
GDP	10.34675	4.7625	19.39936606	-24.11	67.48

Table : Descriptive statistics

For the dependent and independent variables, descriptive statistics are used. The mean, median, maximum, minimum, and standard deviation are all included in the descriptive analysis for each variable. average value of ROA is 0.82% with a standard deviation of 0.42%, the minimum and maximum values are 0.18% and 1.72%, respectively. When the mean ROE is 10.26%, the minimum value is 0.49% and the maximum value is 20.04%. The average of capital adequacy ratio and liquidity ratios is approximately 12.29% and 9.59%, respectively. The cost to income ratio amounts to 52.01% on average.

The means of corporate governance variables over the year 2019 to 2020 is: 12.6 for board size, 24.98 for board meetings, 0.43% for duality and 17.29% for independent directors. Concerning macroeconomic variables, the average growth rate of real GDP is approximately 10.35% over the 2019 to 2020 period.

4.2 pw correlation

4.2.1 Correlation between ROA and independent variables

	<i>ROA</i>	<i>SIZE</i>	<i>CA</i>	<i>LIQ</i>	<i>COST</i>	<i>NPL</i>	<i>BS</i>	<i>MEE</i> <i>T</i>	<i>DUA</i>	<i>IND</i>	<i>GD</i> <i>P</i>
ROA	1										

SIZ E	- 0.320 13	1									
CA	0.597 125	- 0.477 01	1								
LIQ	0.318 743	0.332 141	- 0.062 49	1							
CO ST	- 0.159 56	0.326 027	- 0.381 35	0.103 397	1						
NPL	- 0.289 09	0.580 564	- 0.252	0.291 994	0.236 115	1					
BS	- 0.323 75	- 0.038 47	0.018 944	- 0.182 09	- 0.488 25	- 0.025 15	1				
ME ET	- 0.415 59	0.565 127	- 0.520 93	0.008 396	0.298 395	0.668 16	- 0.17 724	1			
DU A	0.230 15	- 0.390 36	0.194 019	0.060 333	- 0.261 36	- 0.483 88	- 0.19 036	- 0.419 04	1		
IND	0.593 58	- 0.597 89	0.586 452	- 0.156 81	- 0.179 55	- 0.570 05	- 0.36 502	- 0.413 79	0.429 989	1	
GD P	- 0.304 27	0.496 739	- 0.230 35	0.091 561	0.206 288	0.775 457	- 0.06 48	0.726 696	- 0.531 92	- 0.55 781	1

Table: Correlation between ROA and independent variables

4.2.2 Correlations between ROE and independent variables

	<i>ROE</i>	<i>SIZE</i>	<i>CA</i>	<i>LIQ</i>	<i>COST</i>	<i>NPL</i>	<i>BS</i>	<i>MEE</i> <i>T</i>	<i>DUA</i>	<i>IND</i>	<i>GD</i> <i>P</i>
ROE	1										
SIZE	-0.1961	1									
CA	0.557042	-0.47701	1								
LIQ	0.481465	0.332141	-0.06249	1							
COST	0.00687	0.326027	-0.38135	0.103397	1						
NPL	-0.20286	0.580564	-0.252	0.291994	0.236115	1					
BS	-0.18497	-0.03847	0.018944	-0.18209	-0.48825	-0.02515	1				
MEE	-0.45826	0.565127	-0.52093	0.008396	0.298395	0.66816	-0.17724	1			
DUA	0.186806	-0.39036	0.194019	0.060333	-0.26136	-0.48388	-0.19036	-0.41904	1		
IND	0.281514	-0.59789	0.586452	-0.15681	-0.17955	-0.57005	-0.36502	-0.41379	0.429989	1	
GD	-0.15006	0.496739	-0.23035	0.091561	0.206288	0.775457	-0.0648	0.726696	-0.53192	-0.55781	1

Table : Correlations between ROE and independent variables

Interpretation:

Correlations between ROA and independent variables and Correlations between ROE and independent variables present the correlation matrix for the several variables. The results show that there is a negative correlation of ROA and ROE with bank's size board meetings Non-Performing Loans Ratio and GDP per capita growth. When the dependent variables are positively correlated to liquidity, cost to income ratio and independent directors Also capital adequacy is positively correlated to ROA and negatively correlated to ROE, and vice versa for board size .

4.2 Discussion of the results

4.2.1 Comparison of Return on Assets (ROA) of 2019 and 2020 between twenty States owned banks and private Banks:

Bank Names	ROA (2020)	ROA (2019)
BRAC Bank Limited	1.18	1.64
Dutch-Bangla Bank Limited	1.3	1.2
Meghna Bank Limited	0.22	0.19
Prime Bank Limited	0.54	0.54
Mutual Trust Bank Limited	0.37	0.56
One Bank Limited	0.44	0.59
City bank Limited	0.21	0.2
Sonali Bank Limited	0.03	0.33
Janata Bank Limited	1	0.64
Agrani Bank Limited	0.03	0.03
Rupali Bank Limited	1.1	0.7

Table: Comparison of Return on Assets (ROA) of 2019 and 2020

Figure 1: Comparison of Return on Assets (ROA) between 2019 and 2020

Interpretation:

In case of 2020, on this graph we can see that DBBL had the highest return on asset for the year 2020 and Agrani bank limited had lowest return on assets which was 0.03. Others banks had return on assets between 1.66 to 0.02 which where- Dutch-Bangla Bank Limited 1.3, Prime Bank Limited 0.76, Mutual Trust Bank Limited 0.82, One Bank Limited 0.56, City bank Limited 0.7, Sonali Bank Limited 0.18, Janata Bank Limited 0.03, Agrani Bank Limited 1

In case of 2019, on this graph we can see that Agrani Bank Limited had the lowest return on asset for year 2019 and Brac Bank Limited had the highest return on asset which was 1.18. Others bank had return on asset between 0.19 to 1.78 which where- Dutch-Bangla Bank Limited 1.2, Prime Bank Limited 0.38, Mutual Trust Bank Limited 1.08, City bank Limited 1.4, Sonali Bank Limited 0.23, Janata Bank Limited 0.33, Agrani Bank Limited 0.64, Rupali Bank Limited 0.5.

4.2.2 Comparison of Return on Equity (ROE) for 2019 and 2020 between twenty Statesowned banks and Privat Banks:

Bank Names	ROE (2020)	ROE (2019)
BRAC Bank Limited	10.58	15.6
Dutch-Bangla Bank Limited	18.4	17.2
Meghna Bank Limited	8.9	7.6
Prime Bank Limited	6.31	5.93
Mutual Trust Bank Limited	5.83	9.03
One Bank Limited	0.09	0.88
City bank Limited	4.21	3.92
Sonali Bank Limited	0.46	5.23
Janata Bank Limited	16.59	14.54
Agrani Bank Limited	0.92	0.8
Rupali Bank Limited	14.8	9.9

Table 4 : Comparison of Return on Equity (ROE) for 2019 and 2020

Figure 2: Comparison of Return on Equity (ROE) between 2019 and 2020

Interpretation:

In case of 2020, on this graph we can see that One bank had the lowest return on equity on the year 2020 and Dutch Bangla bank had the highest return on equity which was 19.7. Other banks has return on equity between 0.09 to 19.7 which where- BRAC Bank Limited 17.94, Dutch-Bangla Bank Limited 19.7, Meghna Bank Limited 8.9, Prime Bank Limited 8.6, Mutual Trust Bank Limited 13.85, One Bank Limited 0.09, Premier Bank Limited 15.71, City bank Limited 8.2, Sonali Bank Limited 3.32, Janata Bank Limited 0.46, Agrani Bank Limited 16.59, Rupali Bank Limited 0.62

In case of 2019, on this graph we can see that Rupali Bank Limited had the lowest return on equity and BRAC Bank Limited has the highest in year 2019. Other banks has return on equity between 0.84 to 22.14 which where- Dutch-Bangla Bank Limited 13.2, Meghna Bank Limited 7.6, Mutual Trust Bank Limited 18.35, One Bank Limited 0.88, City bank Limited 15.9, Sonali Bank Limited 2.94, Janata Bank Limited 5.23, Agrani Bank Limited 14.5

4.2.3 Comparison of Bank's Size (SIZE) for 2019 and 2020 between twenty States owned banks and Privet Banks:

Bank Names	SIZE (2020)	SIZE (2019)
BRAC Bank Limited	5.56	5.5
Dutch-Bangla Bank Limited	5.54	5.49
Meghna Bank Limited	10.64	8.89
Prime Bank Limited	5.47	5.45
Mutual Trust Bank Limited	5.35	5.3
One Bank Limited	11.42	5.34
City bank Limited	12.12	11.87
Sonali Bank Limited	11.94	5.91
Janata Bank Limited	11.83	10.87
Agrani Bank Limited	9.17	5.58
Rupali Bank Limited	11.51	5.44

Table 5 : Comparison of Bank's Size (SIZE) for 2019 and 2020

Figure 3: Comparison of Bank's Size (SIZE) for 2019 and 2020

Interpretation:

In case of 2020, on this graph we can see that, Sonali Bank Limited had large Bank size for the year 2020 and jumuna bank Limited has the smallest bank size among those twenty banks. Other banks size was between 5.35 to 12.12 which where- BRAC Bank Limited 5.56, Dutch-Bangla Bank Limited 5.54, Eastern Bank Limited 11.46, IFIC Bank Limited 5.45, Meghna Bank Limited 10.64, Prime Bank Limited 5.47, Mutual Trust Bank Limited 5.35, One Bank Limited 11.42, City bank Limited 11.51, Janata Bank Limited 11.94, Agrani Bank Limited 11.83, Rupali Bank Limited 9.17

In case of 2019, on this graph we can see that, city Bank Limited had large Bank size and MTB Limited had lowest Bank size among those twenty banks. Other banks size was between Dhaka Bank Ltd 5.36, BRAC Bank Limited 5.5, Dutch-Bangla Bank Limited 5.49, Meghna Bank Limited 8.89, Prime Bank Limited 5.45, Mutual Trust Bank Limited 5.3, One Bank Limited 5.34, City bank Limited 5.44, Sonali Bank Limited 11.87, Janata Bank Limited 5.91, Agrani Bank Limited 10.87, Rupali Bank Limited 5.58

4.2.4 Comparison of Capital Adequacy (CA) for 2019 and 2020 between twenty States owned banks and Privat Banks:

Bank Names	CA (2020)	CA (2019)
BRAC Bank Limited	15.13	16.16
Dutch-Bangla Bank Limited	17.2	15.5
Meghna Bank Limited	11.31	9.41
Prime Bank Limited	17.28	17.42
Mutual Trust Bank Limited	12.92	12.91
One Bank Limited	13.02	12.8
City bank Limited	10.02	10.09
Sonali Bank Limited	10.09	10.06
Janata Bank Limited	10.24	12.61
Agrani Bank Limited	8.01	10.34
Rupali Bank Limited	15.5	15.2

Table 6 : Comparison of Capital Adequacy (CA) for 2019 and 2020

Figure 4: Comparison of Capital Adequacy (CA) for 2019 and 2020

Interpretation

In case of 2020, on this graph we can see that Dutch-Bangla Bank Limited had highest Capital Adequacy and Sonali Bank Limited had the lowest. Others Capital Adequacy was between them.

Which where- BRAC Bank Limited 14, Dutch-Bangla Bank Limited 15.6, Meghna Bank Limited 11.31, Prime Bank Limited 13.41, Mutual Trust Bank Limited 12.86, National Bank Limited 14.04, One Bank Limited 11.93, City bank Limited 13.4, Sonali Bank Limited 10.1, Janata Bank Limited 10.09, Agrani Bank Limited 10.24, Rupali Bank Limited 10.02

In case of 2019, on this graph we can see that Dutch-Bangla Bank Limited had highest Capital Adequacy and Meghna Bank Limited had the lowest. Others Capital Adequacy was between them. Which where- BRAC Bank Limited 12.31, Dutch-Bangla Bank Limited 14.5, Meghna Bank Limited 9.41, Prime Bank Limited 14.01, Mutual Trust Bank Limited 13.76, One Bank Limited 11.56, City bank Limited 11.25, Southeast Bank Ltd. 10.84, Sonali Bank Limited 11.25, Janata Bank Limited 10.06, Agrani Bank Limited 12.61, Rupali Bank Limited 11.25

4.2.5 Comparison of Liquidity ratio (LIQ) for 2019 and 2020 between twenty States owned banks and Private Banks:

Bank Names	LIQ (2020)	LIQ (2019)
BRAC Bank Limited	12.1	11.67
Dutch-Bangla Bank Limited	3.36	3.11
Meghna Bank Limited	7.44	6.14
Prime Bank Limited	6.21	5.54
Mutual Trust Bank Limited	7.9	6.4
One Bank Limited	4.33	3.43
City bank Limited	7.3	9.64
Sonali Bank Limited	5.92	4.85
Janata Bank Limited	27.86	24.55
Agrani Bank Limited	0.54	0.67
Rupali Bank Limited	14.6	12.8

Table 7: Comparison of Liquidity ratio (LIQ) for 2019 and 2020

Figure 5: Comparison of Liquidity ratio (LIQ) for 2019 and 2020

Interpretation:

In case of 2020, on this graph we can see that Agrani Bank Limited had the highest liquidity ratio and Rupali Bank Limited had the lowest. Other liquidity ratio was between 27.86 to 0.54. Which where-, BRAC Bank Limited 12.1, Dutch-BanglaBank Limited 3.36, Meghna Bank Limited 7.44, Prime Bank Limited 6.21, Mutual Trust Bank Limited 7.9, One Bank Limited 4.33, Premier Bank Limited 17.64, City bank Limited 14.6, Sonali Bank Limited 7.3, Janata Bank Limited 5.92

In case of 2019, on this graph we can see that Agrani Bank Limited had the highest liquidity ratio and Rupali Bank Limited had the lowest. Other liquidity ratio was between 24.55 to 0.67. Which where- BRAC Bank Limited 11.67, Dutch-BanglaBank Limited 3.11, Meghna Bank Limited 6.14, Prime Bank Limited 5.54, Mutual Trust Bank Limited 6.4, One Bank Limited 3.43, City bank Limited 12.8, Southeast Bank Ltd. 4.12, Sonali Bank Limited 9.64, Janata Bank Limited 4.85

4.2.6 Comparison of Operating Management (COST) for 2019 and 2020 between twentyStates owned banks and Privet Banks:

Bank Names	COST (2020)	COST (2019)
BRAC Bank Limited	64	60
Dutch-Bangla Bank Limited	68.1	69.3
Meghna Bank Limited	43.12	55.78
Prime Bank Limited	2.12	1.98
Mutual Trust Bank Limited	50.31	53.82
One Bank Limited	37.41	29.78
City bank Limited	74.13	62.11
Sonali Bank Limited	80.69	78.33
Janata Bank Limited	80.51	75.64
Agrani Bank Limited	88.35	91.21
Rupali Bank Limited	58	53.9

Table 8 : Comparison of Operating Management (COST) for 2019 and 2020

Figure 6: Comparison of Operating Management (COST) for 2019 and 2020

Interpretation:

In case of 2020, on this graph we can see that Rupali Bank Limited had the highest operating cost management and Prime Bank Limited had the lowest. Others operating cost management was between 88.35 to 32.12. Which where- BRAC Bank Limited 64, Dutch-Bangla Bank Limited 68.1Meghna Bank Limited 43.12, Mutual Trust Bank Limited 50.31 National Bank Limited 46.25, One Bank Limited 37.41,City bank Limited 58, Southeast Bank Ltd. 34.61, Sonali Bank Limited 74.13, Janata Bank Limited 80.69, Agrani Bank Limited 80.51

In case of 2019, on this graph we can see that Rupali Bank Limited had the highest operating cost management and Prime Bank Limited had the lowest. Others banks had between 91.21 to 1.98. Which where- BRAC Bank Limited 60, Dutch-Bangla Bank Limited 69.3,Meghna Bank Limited 55.78, Mutual Trust Bank Limited 53.82One Bank Limited 29.78, City bank Limited 53.9,Sonali Bank Limited 62.11, Janata Bank Limited 78.33, Agrani Bank Limited 75.64

4.2.7 Comparison of Non-Performing Loans Ratio (NPL) for 2019and 2020 between twentyStates owned banks and Privet Banks:

Bank Names	NPL (2020)	NPL (2019)
BRAC Bank Limited	2.93	3.99
Dutch-Bangla Bank Limited	2.2	4.4
Meghna Bank Limited	2.6	2.1
Prime Bank Limited	3.46	4.66
Mutual Trust Bank Limited	4.6	5.39
One Bank Limited	11.28	1.25
City bank Limited	18.37	20.32
Sonali Bank Limited	19.5	3.73
Janata Bank Limited	17.45	18.56
Agrani Bank Limited	12.7	16.15
Rupali Bank Limited	4	5.8

Table 9 : Comparison of Non-Performing Loans Ratio (NPL) for 2019and 2020

Figure 7: Comparison of Non-Performing Loans Ratio (NPL) for 2019 and 2020

Interpretation:

In case of 2020, on this graph we can see that Sonali Bank Limited had highest NPL and Rupali Bank Limited had the lowest. Others bank had between 26.26 to 0.17. which where- BRAC Bank Limited 3.1, Dutch-Bangla Bank Limited 4.1, Meghna Bank Limited 2.6, Prime Bank Limited 10.3, Mutual Trust Bank Limited 5.48, One Bank Limited 11.28, Premier Bank Limited 3.99, Citybank Limited 3.1, Sonali Bank Limited 26.26, Janata Bank Limited 19.5, Agrani Bank Limited 17.45, Rupali Bank Limited 0.17

In case of 2019, on this graph we can see that Sonali Bank Limited had highest NPL and Rupali Bank Limited had the lowest. Others bank had between 29.48 to 0.26. Which where- BRAC Bank Limited 3.56, Dutch-Bangla Bank Limited 4.7, Meghna Bank Limited 2.1, Prime Bank Limited 5.45, Mutual Trust Bank Limited 4.3 One Bank Limited 1.25, Premier Bank Limited 3.49, City bank Limited 5.4, Janata Bank Limited 3.73, Agrani Bank Limited 18.56

4.2.8 Comparison of Board Size (BS) for 2019 and 2020 between twenty States owned banks and Privat Banks:

Bank Names	BS (2020)	BS (2019)
BRAC Bank Limited	16	17
Dutch-Bangla Bank Limited	15	14
Meghna Bank Limited	20	18
Prime Bank Limited	14	22
Mutual Trust Bank Limited	16	15
One Bank Limited	24	25
City bank Limited	58	46
Sonali Bank Limited	48	48
Janata Bank Limited	23	26
Agrani Bank Limited	24	21
Rupali Bank Limited	22	25

Table 10 : Comparison of Board Size (BS) for 2019 and 2020

Figure 8: Comparison of Board Size (BS) for 2019 and 2020

Interpretation:

In case of 2020, on this graph we can see that Prime Bank Limited had highest board size, Dutch-Bangla Bank Limited and Prime Bank Limited had the lowest. Other banks had between 7 to 21. Which where BRAC Bank Limited 9, Meghna Bank Limited 20, Mutual Trust Bank Limited 12, One Bank Limited 9, City bank Limited 13, Southeast Bank Ltd. 12, Sonali Bank Limited 14, Janata Bank Limited 8, Agrani Bank Limited 10, Rupali Bank Limited 11

In case of 2020, on this graph we can see that Meghna Bank Limited had highest board size and Dutch-Bangla Bank Limited had the lowest. Other banks had between 7 to 20. Which where- BRAC Bank Limited 8, Prime Bank Limited 18, Mutual Trust Bank Limited 13, One Bank Limited 9, City bank Limited 14, Southeast Bank Ltd. 12, Sonali Bank Limited 14, Janata Bank Limited 10, Agrani Bank Limited 10, Rupali Bank Limited 11

4.2.9 Comparison of Board Meetings (MEET) for 2019 and 2020 between twenty Statesowned banks and Privat Banks:

Bank Names	MEET (2020)	MEET (2019)
BRAC Bank Limited	9	8
Dutch-Bangla Bank Limited	7	7
Meghna Bank Limited	20	20
Prime Bank Limited	21	18
Mutual Trust Bank Limited	12	13
One Bank Limited	9	9
City bank Limited	14	14
Sonali Bank Limited	8	10
Janata Bank Limited	10	10
Agrani Bank Limited	11	11
Rupali Bank Limited	13	14

Table 11 : Comparison of Board Meetings (MEET) for 2019 and 2020

Figure 9: Comparison of Board Meetings (MEET) for 2019 and 2020

Interpretation:

In case of 2020, on this graph we can see that Sonali Bank Limited had arranged highest board meeting and Prime Bank Limited had arranged lowest. Other banks had between 58 to 14. Which where- BRAC Bank Limited 16, Dutch-Bangla Bank Limited 15, Meghna Bank Limited 20, Mutual Trust Bank Limited 16, One Bank Limited 24, Premier Bank Limited 14, City bank Limited 22, Janata Bank Limited 48, Agrani Bank Limited 23, Rupali Bank Limited 24

In case of 2020, on this graph we can see that Janata Bank Limited had arranged highest board meeting and Dutch-Bangla Bank Limited had arranged lowest. Other banks had between 48 to 14. Which where- BRAC Bank Limited 17, Meghna Bank Limited 18, Prime Bank Limited 22, Mutual Trust Bank Limited 15, One Bank Limited 25, City bank Limited 25, Southeast Bank Ltd. 29, Sonali Bank Limited 46, Agrani Bank Limited 26, Rupali Bank Limited 21

4.2.10 Comparison of per capita growth (GDP) for 2020 and 2019 between twenty States owned banks and Privet Banks:

Bank Names	GDP (2020)	GDP (2019)
BRAC Bank Limited	5.7	2.6
Dutch-Bangla Bank Limited	10.5	19.86
Meghna Bank Limited	-4.52	6.49
Prime Bank Limited	6.15	6.25
Mutual Trust Bank Limited	2.35	4.17
One Bank Limited	1.83	2.64
City bank Limited	-4.72	-3.73
Sonali Bank Limited	18.99	115.97
Janata Bank Limited	13.5	91.03
Agrani Bank Limited	2.3	30.82
Rupali Bank Limited	-39	-9.22

Table 12 : Comparison of per capita growth (GDP) for 2019 and 2020

Figure 10: Comparison of per capita growth (GDP) for 2019 and 2020

Interpretation:

In case of 2020, on this graph we can see that Sonali Bank Limited had highest GDP and RupaliBank Limited had lowest which was negative GDP. Other Banks had between -39 to 18.99. Whichwhere-BRAC Bank Limited 5.7, Dutch-BanglaBank Limited 10.5, Prime Bank Limited 6.15, Mutual Trust Bank Limited 2.35, One Bank Limited 1.83, City bank Limited -4.72, Janata Bank Limited 13.5, Agrani Bank Limited 2.3.

In case of 2019, on this graph we can see that Sonali Bank Limited had highest GDP and Rupali Bank Limited had lowest which was negative GDP. Other Banks had between -9.22 to 115.97. Which where- BRAC Bank Limited 2.6, Dutch-Bangla Bank Limited 19.86, Meghna Bank Limited 6.49, Prime Bank Limited 6.25, Mutual Trust Bank Limited 4.17, National Bank Limited -1.22, One Bank Limited 2.64, City bank Limited -3.73, Janata Bank Limited 91.03, Agrani Bank Limited 30.82

4.2.11 Comparison of IND for 2020 and 2019 between twenty States owned banks and Privet Banks:

Bank Names	IND (2020)	IND (2019)
BRAC Bank Limited	33	38
Dutch-Bangla Bank Limited	29	29
Meghna Bank Limited	0	0
Prime Bank Limited	19	17
Mutual Trust Bank Limited	8	15
One Bank Limited	22	22
City bank Limited	0	0
Sonali Bank Limited	0	0
Janata Bank Limited	0	0
Agrani Bank Limited	27.27	25.47
Rupali Bank Limited	15.38	14.29

Table 13: Comparison of IND for 2019 and 2020

Figure 11: Comparison of IND for 2019 and 2020

Interpretation:

In case of 2020, on this graph we can see that Brac Bank Limited had highest IND Other Banks had between 15 to 34. Whichwhere-BRAC Bank Limited 33 , Dutch-BanglaBank Limited 29, Prime Bank

Limited 19, Mutual Trust Bank Limited 8, One Bank Limited 22, Agrani Bank Limited 27.27.

In case of 2019, on this graph we can see that Brac Bank Limited had highest IND and Other Banks had between 14 to 39. Which where- BRAC Bank Limited 38 , Dutch-Bangla Bank Limited 29, Prime Bank Limited 17, Mutual Trust Bank Limited 15 , One Bank Limited 22 Agrani Bank Limited 30.82

Chapter 5 finding

During research work, I have found the followings:

- Basically, the size of the bank is calculated as a natural logarithm of the overall asset value. Bank size has a negative relationship between dependent variables, according to the empirical section. That implies that the size of the bank did effect on the success of the banking industry in Bangladesh.
- I learned from the theoretical portion that liquidity is positively linked to both ROE and ROA. Bangladeshi banks should be very careful to raise the amount of loans in the event of a bad performance, since it brings in a decrease in profitability. This is because Bangladeshi banks have suffered large losses from rising rates of non-performing loans. Banks currently have a lot of capital, but little incentive to use their assets.
- One of the bank-specific variables affecting the level of bank profitability is CAR. In both cases, we find good capital adequacy ratio outcomes according to the findings of correlation analysis, panel and multiple regression analysis. The capital adequacy ratio has a positive effect on the output of Bangladeshi banks because of the positive outcome, which is statistically important, contrary to predictions. The finding indicates that lower profitability is caused or expected by a higher capital ratio.
- I observed from the empirical portion that in both research methods (correlation and panel regression), the non-performing loan negative relationship between dependent variables and independent variables was observed. That means a non-performing loan that affects Bangladesh's banking efficiency.
- In case of COST, there is a positive relation between dependent variables. That means COST did not influence negatively the banking sector of Bangladesh.
- Negative relationships between dependent and independent variables occur in the case of a board meeting. Any banks are very serious about their operations and schedule more than 25

board meetings a year. But in Bangladesh, there are several banks that have not scheduled more than 15 meetings in a few years. That's why banking success in Bangladesh is influenced by this aspect.

- In case of Duality, there is a negative relation between dependent variables. That means duality did affect the banking sector performance of Bangladesh
- I find that GDP has a positive relationship between dependent and independent variables with the use of both the correlation analysis method and the panel and multiple regression analysis method. That means that the GDP has not influenced the performance of Bangladesh's banking sector. Moreover, from my above investigation I have found that bank size, non-performing loan, board size, board meeting, duality and independent variables has a negative relation with dependent variables ROA and ROE. That means those variables influencing the performance of banking industry negatively in Bangladesh

Chapter 6: concluding remarks

This report is a minor contribution to ongoing discussions in Bangladesh regarding banking efficiency during pandemics. The analysis examines the effect on the efficiency of Bangladeshi banks of bank-specific characteristics, bank governance, bank-specific determinants, and economic conditions. Many of those attributes were calculated by asset return and equity return. Correlation matrix and Panel data regression methods were applied to find the outcome on the basis of 11 observations of banks and private banks in Bangladesh between 2019 and 2020. This study confirms that we have seen from past results that bank management cost decisions are influential in affecting Bangladesh's bank efficiency. I observed that the cost to income ratio, non-performing loan ratio, board size and board meeting were highly important and negatively linked to the success of the bank in Bangladesh in the analytical section. In addition, this analysis found a strong and relevant relationship between the size of the deposits and the profitability calculated by asset value and equity return. Bank scale, capital adequacy ratio, independent directors and growth rate of profit have no major impact on the efficiency of Bangladeshi banks on the remaining bank-specific factors. Corporate governance established guidelines that determine how a company runs. In another word, The method through which firms are directed and governed is known as corporate governance. The aim of corporate governance is to enable effective, entrepreneurial, and responsible management that will ensure the company's long-term prosperity. Governance in the workplace has become a topic of increasing interest among the policy makers since it looks at the relationship between the board of directors, shareholders and management.

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